

Harun Kk. *Science without Leisure: Practical Naturalism in Istanbul, 1660-1732*. Pittsburgh: University of Pittsburgh Press, 2019. 324 s., ISBN: 9780822945802.

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“ ” Taylan, İŐin. “Harun Kk. *Science without Leisure: Practical Naturalism in Istanbul, 1660-1732*.” *Zemin*, s. 2 (2021): 266-269.

Harun Küçük's book *Science without Leisure: Practical Naturalism in Istanbul, 1660-1732* is one of the few English monographs on the history of science in the Ottoman Empire. The book examines early modern science in Istanbul, covering the period between 1660 and 1732, from the Great Fire to the Patrona [Halil] Revolt. While focusing on the scientific practices, the author demonstrates the distinctive nature of science in Istanbul, namely the absence of natural philosophy and the prevalence of practical naturalism. According to the author, scholars in Istanbul in the seventeenth and eighteenth century could not engage in contemporary scientific practices, such as natural philosophy, theoretical astronomy, and theoretical medicine, because of the lack of "leisure," a concept that the author defines as "the efficacious freedom to have intellectual pursuits" (p. 7). Thus, the author asks: What is the nature of science in a context where leisure is absent?

Küçük organizes his book around three parts and eight chapters. In the first three chapters, he provides the reader with Istanbul's social, cultural, and economic background, followed by a study of medreses and scholars in the city. The following two chapters, "The Calendar" and "The Recipe," provide a case study on seventeenth-century astronomy, namely a study of Tezkireci İbrahim's partial Turkish translation of Duret's *Nouvelle théorie des planètes* (Kandilli Manuscript 403) and an overview of new medicine in the seventeenth century. Then, based on his study of the practices of medicine and astronomy in the seventeenth century, Küçük builds on the concept of practical naturalism. The last two chapters further support his case for practical naturalism, especially by drawing on Yirmisekiz Mehmed Çelebi and İbrahim Müteferrika's scientific translations.

The book fundamentally conceptualizes the impact of monetary inflation on the scientific practices in seventeenth and eighteenth-century Istanbul. It does this by critically engaging with the concept of "leisure." The author expands on Bourdieu's definition of leisure, "free time, freed from the urgencies of the world, that allows a free and liberated relation to those urgencies and to the world" (p. 11) and also reframes this approach from a more materialist perspective by stressing the economic factors informing leisure practices. Thus, Küçük further defines leisure along the lines of "having leisure time, and producing what [he] call[s] the leisure to engage in a very specific kind of nonproductive work." (p. 6). This materialist reading finds its argument in the claim that "the most

fundamental leisure science is natural philosophy” (p. 41), explaining the underdevelopment of theoretical works in Istanbul. A complementary key concept is “practical naturalism.” Küçük uses practical naturalism as an “important middle term,” and defines it as “neither quite artisanal knowledge nor quite applied science, nor yet popular science” (p. 4). Overall, taking “leisure” as a conceptual departing point, the author develops a fresh approach to illuminate the nature of scientific engagement, namely, practical naturalism, in early modern Istanbul.

Throughout the book, the author uses a diverse spectrum of primary and secondary sources to prove the impact of monetary inflation on scholarly activity. The wide range of primary sources, in particular, is intriguing: Küçük studies the Kandilli Manuscript, Tezkireci İbrahim’s partial Turkish translation of Duret’s *Nouvelle théorie des planètes*, side by side with İbrahim Müteferrika’s printed *Füyuzat-ı Mıknatısiye, Magnetic Effluvia*, a translation of Christoph Eberhard’s *Specimen Theoriae Magneticae*, as well as Nabi’s poetry, and edicts of Sultan Murad III. He further draws on Hezarfenn Hüseyin’s comments on the relationship between inflation and professor salaries, and graphs representing the nominal salaries (at Süleymaniye Medreses) against actual prices. Further comparing the purchasing power of Ali Kuşçu (a fifteenth-century scholar under the patronage of Mehmed II) and the seventeenth-century Ottoman scholars, Küçük demonstrates that the Ottoman scholars could not have been engaged in natural philosophy in the seventeenth century.

As a reader, I appreciate that the author focuses on Istanbul and avoids generalized approaches to the Ottoman lands or the Islamic world, and “Islamic science as a coherent category” (p. 23). This focus helps the author successfully navigate the heavily-loaded categories of Westernization, the Scientific Revolution, and Enlightenment. By studying “the social transformations that had taken place in Istanbul within three generations,” Küçük argues that “transformations ... had nothing to do with the West” (p. 4). He could have easily contextualized his study in an early modern European science context, as he writes, “I could have made the claim that the Ottoman Empire had gone through its own scientific revolution—thus blending it into familiar narratives” (p. 229). Along similar lines, Küçük concludes that “this leaves us with a curious beast, a culture of early modern practical naturalism in Istanbul that was somehow neither specifically European nor specifically Islamic, nor yet generally Ottoman” (p. 48). At this point in historiography, when the overall trend is to emphasize connections,

global, early modern or Islamicate, Küçük's decision to stay away from such a framework is noteworthy: While carrying the risk of returning to a *sui-generis* understanding of Ottoman history, it sure offers a fresh framework. This choice actually helps Küçük to provide an original contribution to the history of science as a larger field. Rather than reformulating existing loaded categories or reiterating the accustomed names of European early modern science, he opens a discussion on the conceptualization of science and its relation to theory, further calling for a "discussion of necessary and sufficient conditions" for certain scientific practices to take place (p. 8). Moreover, Küçük provides a reinterpretation of the seventeenth-century European science, and that, according to him, "was not innovation or rationalism; it was, rather, accumulation and preservation of knowledge and to a lesser extent, providing access to this knowledge" (p. 9).

The book reads very well: Together with Küçük's narrative flow, his translation choices also facilitate the reading for the general audience. Some of his translations are relatively liberal; for instance, he calls the Ottoman *medrese hocası* a professor. Similarly, he translates some other works rather freely, like *Cihannüma* to *Cosmorama*—not to mention the comparison between the seventeenth-century *medrese* and the Ivy League institutions. His comments on "the grim state of the scholarly profession" (p. 105) presented in the "Some Presentist Remarks" at the end of his monograph makes his argument cautiously "presentist," but also interesting, especially these days, when his comment that "Istanbul, and Turkey more generally, has never left the shadow of the seventeenth-century slump" (p. 231) applies more than ever. Yet still, the book's overemphasis on monetary inflation comes at the expense of other potential factors that might have informed scholastic tendencies in the seventeenth century Istanbul, that is exemplified in the case "new tastes did not cause significant changes, because Istanbul's professors were still not being paid well" (p. 172).

This book is a significant contribution to Ottoman historiography and the larger field of early modern science. The author extends his readership to historians of science, especially by providing a reinterpretation of "science" and alternative practices of early modern science, and paves the way for young scholars to investigate local contexts for indigenous scientific practices. Thus, this book would also be useful not only for Ottomanists but also for all scholars interested in the history of science.